

A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE RETENTION AS A TOOL FOR IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS: ANALYTICAL STUDY AT VAIGAI AGRO PRODUCT LIMITED

M. Saravanan*, P. T. J. K. Lilian & Dr. B. Velmurugan*****

* PG Scholar, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

*** Associate Professor & HOD, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: M. Saravanan, P. T. J. K. Lilian & Dr. B. Velmurugan, "A Study on Employee Retention as a Tool for Improving Organizational Effectiveness: Analytical Study at Vaigai Agro Product Limited", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 8, Issue 1, Page Number 78-82, 2023.

Abstract:

Human sources are those who make the group of workers of a company. It's also recognized via manpower, skills, labour, employees, etc. Human Resource department of a business enterprise performs human useful resource control. It entails various elements of the employment consisting of compliance with labour regulation and employment standards, management of worker benefits, and various other sports related to recruitment and choice of the employee. Worker retention is regarding the efforts with the aid of which employers try and retain the personnel in their team of workers. Retention turns into the strategies in place of the final results. Preserving the worker for long duration of time is known as retention. Retention strategies of the organization need to have the capacity to attract and hold their staff. Organizational effectiveness refers to a company's ability to achieve the goals it sets out to achieve. It's far the performance of the organization, group or an organization to fulfill its goal. Six Sigma is a methodology that makes a specialty of improving the overall efficiency of a business process.

Introduction:

Long-term health and success of any organization depends upon the retention of key employees. To a great extent customer satisfaction, organizational performance in terms of increased sales, satisfied colleagues and reporting staff, effective succession planning etc., is dependent upon the ability to retain the best employees in any organization. Encouraging employees to remain in the organization for a long period of time can be termed as employee retention. It is a process in which the employees are encouraged to remain with the organization for the maximum period of time or until the completion of the project.

Models of Employees' Retention:

There are three important models on employee retention, one of them is a) Zinger Model and the other is 2) ERC's Retention Model. 3) Integrated System for Retaining Employees. A brief explanation of these models is follows:

Zinger Model:

Employee retention is the art and science of engaging people in authentic and recognized connections to strategy, roles, performance, organization, community, relationship, customers, development, energy, and well-being as companies leverage, sustain, and transform their work connections into results.

Figure 1: Zinger Model

According to the Zinger Model, employee retention is directed towards achieving results of the organization that the department, team, or individual wants to achieve. To achieve results, companies need to craft a strategy to get there. A central key of employee retention is connection. In some cases connection is

synonymous with engagement. Engagement is not a onetime survey measure or a steady state. To engage is to fully experience and contribute to the dynamic elements of work.

ERC's Retention Model:

Employee Retention Connection's model concentrates on applied organizational experience indicating three primary drivers of employee retention, Work can be made stimulating by giving variety of assignments, autonomy to make decisions, resources and support provided to do good work, opportunity to learn, feedback on result and understanding the significance of one's personal contributions.

Integrated System for Retaining Employees:

The Employee Retention Connection transforms the organization culture and enhances the competitive edge through the following five -phased approach: ERC begins by analyzing the organization's motivation and retention culture through surveys and focus groups that is the motivating and demotivating aspects of the culture. ERC concentrates on designing high-involvement job and work assignments and trains supervisors and managers in proven methods of motivational leadership.

Statement of the Problem:

Employee's retention refers to the techniques employed by the management to help the employees stay with the organization for a longer period of time. Employee retention strategies go a long way in motivating the employees so that they stick to the organization for the maximum time and contribute effectively. Sincere efforts must be taken to ensure growth and learning for the employees in their current assignments and for them to enjoy their work.

Objectives of the Study:

Primary Objectives:

- A study on employee retention strategy of Vaighai Agro Products Limited at Madurai

Secondary Objectives:

- To know the employee retention practices followed in the company
- To know the welfare facilities provided by this organization are satisfactory
- To study the Work-life balance is supported by this organization
- To know the Interpersonal relationship are encourage in this organization
- To identify the factors related to the retention of employees
- To analyse the reasons for retention among the employees
- To suggest good employee retention strategy to the organization

Need of the Study:

The need of this study lies in the gist of the agro industry in recent years, were on one hand the employee turnover has been alarmingly high, thus affecting the organization a lot. Many empirical studies have

been made on various parts of the world in connection with different concepts of Human resource management, but in previous researches there exists a gap that most literature sources address the topic of retention merely by concentrating in-depth on retention factors and strategies that could be used by organizations to motivate employees. Despite of the high importance attached to the concept of Retention strategies, and the importance of retention and its factors focusing on improve retention rate in the company. This study is an attempt to access the patterns of work place retention factors and strategies in the company and to analyse the relationship between employee retention and indicators of employee retention such as employee performance, employee commitment, employee satisfaction, employee participation and employee morale. The end result of this study will make it easier for managers to identify what motivates the employee and how the implementation of such motivational factors can lead to higher levels of employee retention accompanied by increased performance, morale and satisfaction.

Scope of the Study:

This study conducted for identifying the study on employee retention of Vaighai Agro Products Limited. In this project mainly focuses on employee's retention strategies and to find why the employees leave the organisation. This study helps the employers to build new strategy for retaining the employees in the organisation. To analyse the chosen topic, this research are mostly from middle level. The retention of employees to be analysed to make certain things that they put together a system that can keep an accurate count of individual employee's retention.

Hypothesis of the Study:

- Null Hypothesis HO: There is significance relationship between educational qualification of the respondents and management encourages employee participation.
- Alternative Hypothesis H1: There is no significance relationship between educational qualification of the respondents and management encourage employee participation

Research Design:

“A Research Design is the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with the economy in procedure”. The research design adopted for the studies is descriptive design. The researcher has to describe the present situation in order to know the behaviour of the consumers. Hence descriptive research study is used. Descriptive research can only report what has happened and what is happening.

Research Methodology:

Research Methodology is a systematic way to solve a research problem; it includes various steps that are generally adopted by a researcher in studying the problem along with the logic behind them. The present study was conducted at the manufacturing firm.

Method of Data Collection:

- Primary Data: Primary data means data which is fresh collected data. Primary data mainly been collected through Questionnaire, surveys etc.
- Secondary Data: Secondary data means the data that are already available. Generally speaking secondary data is collected by some organizations or agencies which have already been processed when the researcher utilizes secondary data; the process of secondary data collection and analysis is called desk research.

Sampling:

The aggregate elementary units in the survey are referred to as the population. Here it covers the entire employees of Vaighai Agro Products Limited at Madurai.

Sample Size:

The study based only on the opinion and expectation of consumer. Total number of sample taken for the study is 150 respondents.

Sample Design:

Convenience sampling techniques were used for the study.

Tools Used for Research:

- Simple Percentage Method
- Correlation
- Chi Square test

Company Profile:

Founded in 1980, Vaighai Agro is currently “India's largest rice bran processor” with state-of-the-art Manufacturing facilities spread across South India. Notably, we have consistently bagged the “Highest Rice Bran Processors of India” award from the SEA, India, since 2009. Incepted with the express purpose of manufacturing and supplying rice bran oil and de-oiled bran products, Vaighai Agro has been instrumental in shifting India's agribusiness industry from a model of dependency to self-sufficiency. The organization has exceptional quality assurance and fully-equipped R&D facilities with international-standard testing and research assets managed by a team of skilled professionals. Our reputable quality assurance framework assures the

superior quality and integrity of the products we deliver to our clientele. In addition, our on-going innovation efforts are designed to satisfy the evolving needs of our clients most efficiently and productively.

Review of Literature:

Professionals in Pakistan. Van Dick et al. (2020) in their article “Should I stay or should I go? Explaining turnover intentions with corporation identification and Employee opinion.” have also identified the employee opinion as a predictor of retention; however, they argue that it is a mediating variable between organizational identification and retention process. According to their study, organizational identification feeds into employee opinion, which, in turn, predicts retention and selection process.

Abdul Rahman, Raza Naqvi, and Ismail Ramay (2021) in their article “Measuring turnover intention: A study of it professionals in Pakistan.” revealed that Employee opinion and organizational retention had a negative effect on retention process and selection, whereas perceived alternative job opportunities had a significant positive correlation with Employee opinion in retention procedure.

Electra D. Paskett (2021) Being an agent in India is seen as a societal stigma as there is uncertainty of employee retention and income attached to it. People join companies as a part time job or a gap filler occupation and not as a long-term career. Very few competent people want to become agents owing to low social status attached to it. It is a high-pressure job. It is expected from an agent to understand the customer’s needs and sell the products accordingly.

Jennifer Roberts (2022) The expectation achievement gap adds to the retention. Many people are lured to the profession with a high earning potential. However, to earn a decent income, agents require a lot of patience, perseverance, and persuasion in the field. During early phase, the earnings of the agents are low despite hard work.

Cathy J. Bradley (2022) scarce skilled or experienced human resource in market leads to wide scale poaching and head hunting amongst the competitors. The industry has yet to witness mature HR processes, like work force planning, training, Retention, and retention. The lack of replanted retention leads the firms to indulge in poaching human resources working in other firms. With having a high percentage of the workforce from multiple sectors (non-domain), the chances of losing employees to other fields, like Fast Moving Consumer Goods companies or other financial outfits, are high.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Chart 1: Employee Work Loads are Distributed Fairly

The above table shows that 24% of the respondents are strongly agree, 36% of the respondents are agree, 26% of the respondents are neutral, 6% of the respondents are disagree and 8% of the respondents are strongly disagree. Thus the majority 36% of the respondents are agree with workloads are distributed fairly.

Chart 2: Management Encourage Employee Participation

The above table shows that 38% of the respondents are strongly agree, 28% of the respondents are agree, 17.4% of the respondents are neutral, 6.5% of the respondents are disagree and 11% of the respondents are strongly disagree. Thus the majority 38% of the respondents are strongly agree with management encourage employee participation.

Conclusion:

The research has a humble attempt in identifying the cause of employees retention and up with a few suggestions. It exists a high level of employees' retention strategies. So, the management has simply to concretize people appropriately, identify the problems, and appreciate the need to resolve it, identify the factors and contributing to the problem and behave in ways that would either eliminate the casual variables or reduce their influence on the problems. Though slow, the process of concretization is sure to produce the desired results conducted in proper ways. Employees comprise the most vital assets of the company. In a work place where employees are not able to use their full potential and not heard and valued, they are likely to leave because of stress and frustration. They need transparent work environment to work in. in a transparent environment where employees get a sense of achievement and belongings, where they can best utilize their potential and realized their skills. They love to be the essential part of such organisation and the company is benefited with a stronger, reliable work force harbouring bright new ideas for its growth.

References:

1. Hiro Lee (1997) - Journal of Development Economics, Volume 52, Issue 1, February 1997, Pages 65–82.
2. James A Schmitz Jr, (2001) - Journal of Monetary Economics, Volume 47, Issue 1, February 2001, Pages 163–187.
3. Eric V. Edmonds (2006) - Journal of International Economics, Volume 69, Issue 2, July 2006, Pages 272–295
4. Gabriele Cardullo (2011) - Labour Economics, Volume 18, Issue 2, April 2011, Pages 205–217
5. William C. Terry (2011) - Geoforum, „Geographic limits to global labor market flexibility“, Volume 42, Issue 6, November 2011, Pages 660–670